

1-Nitroso-2-naphtholate complexes of ruthenium(II) : Synthesis, isomerization and, spectral and electrochemical properties

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Abstract : Reaction of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (Hnn) with $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2]$ in 2 : 1 mole ratio in refluxing ethanol affords two geometrical isomers of a complex of type $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$, in which the 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligand is coordinated to ruthenium as a mono-anionic bidentate N,O-donor. The two isomers are labeled as *ttt* and *cct*, indicating respectively *trans-trans-trans* and *cis-cis-trans* disposition of the N, O and P donor atoms around the metal center. Structures of both the *ttt* and *cct* isomers of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complex have been determined by X-ray crystallography. This *cct* isomer is found to be energetically less stable, and is quantitatively convertible into the thermodynamically more stable *ttt* isomer simply by refluxing in *ortho*-xylene. Both the *ttt*- and *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complexes are diamagnetic, and show characteristic ^1H NMR spectra. They also show intense absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet regions. Cyclic voltammetry on the *ttt*- and *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complexes shows an oxidative response near 0.8 V vs SCE and a reductive response within -0.3 to -0.5 V vs SCE. DFT calculations have been carried out to explain the electronic spectral, as well as electrochemical, observations.

Keywords : 1-Nitroso-2-naphthol, ruthenium, bis-complex, geometrical isomers, crystal structures, spectral and electrochemical properties.

Introduction

There has been considerable current interest in the chemistry of ruthenium complexes¹, mainly because of their fascinating redox, photochemical and catalytic properties. All these properties are dependent largely on the accessibility and inter-convertibility of the different oxidation states of ruthenium, which, in turn, are dependent on the coordination environment around the metal center. Complexation of ruthenium by ligands of different types is of particular importance in this respect. For the present study, which has emerged from our continued interest in the chemistry of ruthenium complexes², we have selected 1-nitroso-2-naphthol as the principal ligand. This ligand is abbreviated as **Hnn**, where H stands for the dissociable phenolic proton. 1-Nitroso-2-naphthol is known to bind to metal centers, via dissociation of the acidic proton, as a mono-anionic N,O-donor forming stable five-membered chelate ring (**I**)³. It is interesting to note here that though a localized charge description of the 1-

nitroso-2-naphtholate anion is presented in **I**, it is actually resonance stabilized. The negative charge, generated primarily on the phenolate-oxygen, as shown in the nitroso-phenolate form (**A**), gets delocalized up to the nitroso-oxygen in the keto-oximate form (**B**). Hence this anionic ligand is best represented in terms of the resonance-hybrid (**C**). Due to the dominant keto-oximate character, 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate anion displays significant difference in its electronic nature compared to another N,O-donor phenolate ligand, viz. quinolin-8-olate anion. For example, the +3 state of ruthenium is stabilized in the tris-quinolin-8-olate complex^{2o,4}, while in the tris-1-nitroso-2-naphtholate complex, the +2 state gets stabilized^{3b}. This has encouraged us to explore chemistry of the 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate complexes of ruthenium further, and the present work is a partial outcome of this exploration. The main objective of the present study has been to synthesize a bis-1-nitroso-2-naphtholate complex of ruthenium, with triphenylphosphine (PPh_3) as the ancillary ligand, and

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study the electronic spectral and redox properties of the complex. In order to interact with the selected 1-nitroso-2-naphthol ligand, $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2]$ has been chosen as the ruthenium starting material, primarily because of its demonstrated ability to undergo facile reaction with such bidentate ligands (say **HL** in general) and afford mixed-ligand complexes of type $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{L})_2]$ ⁵. Reaction of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol with $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2]$ has indeed afforded mixed-ligand complexes of the targeted type, and herein we describe the chemistry of these complexes, with special reference to their formation, structures, isomerization and, spectral and electrochemical properties.

Experimental

Materials :

Ruthenium trichloride was obtained from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, India. Triphenylphosphine and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol were procured respectively from Merck, India, and Loba-Chemie, Mumbai, India. $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_3\text{Cl}_2]$ was synthesized by following a reported procedure⁶. Tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBHP), obtained from Aldrich, and AR grade acetonitrile, procured from Merck, India, were used for electrochemical work. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received.

Syntheses of complexes :

ttt- and *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$: To a solution of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (18 mg, 0.10 mmol) in hot ethanol (30

mL), $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ (50 mg, 0.05 mmol) was added. The mixture was then refluxed for 2 h to yield a purple solution. Evaporation of solvent from this solution gave a purple solid, which was subjected to purification by thin layer chromatography on a silica plate. With benzene as the eluant, two purple bands separated. The first band was extracted with acetonitrile, and evaporation of this extract yielded *ttt*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ as a dark crystalline solid. Similarly, extraction of the second band with acetonitrile followed by its evaporation gave *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$.

ttt- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$: Yield : 9%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{P}_2\text{Ru}$: C, 69.35; H, 4.33; N, 2.88. Found : C, 69.89; H, 4.37; N, 2.92%; ¹H NMR⁷ : 8.87 (1H, d, *J* 9.0), 7.68 (1H, t, *J* 7.5), 7.55–6.94 (30H (2PPh₃) + 3H)*, 6.48 (1H, d, *J* 9.0); IR : 1737, 1540, 1475, 1386, 1291, 1096, 875, 802, 748, 722, 695, 543 and 520 cm⁻¹.

cct- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$: Yield : 17%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{42}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{P}_2\text{Ru}$: C, 69.35; H, 4.33; N, 2.88. Found : C, 69.26; H, 4.38; N, 2.85%; ¹H NMR : 8.84 (1H, d, *J* 9.0), 7.49–6.94 (30H (2PPh₃) + 4H)*, 6.47 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz); IR : 1610, 1592, 1547, 1501, 1435, 1390, 1299, 1207, 1140, 1128, 1096, 1061, 873, 827, 745, 695, 613 and 520 cm⁻¹.

Physical measurements :

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a Sherwood MK-1

balance. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 solution on a Bruker Avance DPX 300 NMR spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Two spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-570 spectrophotometer. Electrochemical measurements were made using a CH Instruments model 600A electrochemical analyzer. A platinum disc working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in the cyclic voltammetry experiments. All electrochemical experiments were performed under a dinitrogen atmosphere. All electrochemical data were collected at 298 K and are uncorrected for junction potentials. Optimization of ground-state structures and energy calculations for both the complexes were carried out by density functional theory (DFT) method using the Gaussian 03 (B3LYP/SDD-6-31G) package⁸.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals of *ttt*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] were obtained by slow evaporation of solvents from a solution of the complex in acetonitrile-ethanol (1 : 1). Single crystals of *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] were obtained by slow evaporation of solvent from a solution of the complex in acetonitrile. Selected crystal data and data collection parameters are given in Table 1. Data were collected on a Bruker SMART CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo K_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). X-Ray data reduction and, structure solution and refinement were done using SHELXS-97 and SHELXL-97 programs⁹. The structures were solved by the direct methods.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

As delineated in the introduction, the present work was undertaken with the intention of synthesizing a bis-1-nitroso-2-naphtholate complex of ruthenium having PPh₃ as the ancillary ligand, and studying its spectral and electrochemical properties. Accordingly a reaction of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (**Hnn**) with [Ru(PPh₃)₃Cl₂] was carried out in 2 : 1 mole ratio in refluxing ethanol, which proceeded smoothly and afforded two purple complexes, presently referred to as purple-1 and purple-2¹⁰, which were purified by chromatography. The combined yield of these two complexes has been decent¹¹. Preliminary char-

Table 1. Crystallographic data for the *ttt*- and *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complexes

	<i>ttt</i> -[Ru(PPh ₃) ₂ (nn) ₂]	<i>cct</i> -[Ru(PPh ₃) ₂ (nn) ₂]
Empirical formula	C ₅₆ H ₄₂ N ₂ O ₄ P ₂ Ru.H ₂ O	C ₅₆ H ₄₂ N ₂ O ₄ P ₂ Ru
Formula mass	987.93	969.93
Crystal system	Triclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	P $\bar{1}$	P2 ₁ /n
<i>a</i> (Å)	9.530(4)	11.7653(4)
<i>b</i> (Å)	11.692(5)	15.0100(6)
<i>c</i> (Å)	11.983(5)	25.8532(9)
α (deg)	105.303(11)	90
β (deg)	108.711(10)	97.341(2)
γ (deg)	99.941(11)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1170.4(9)	4528.2(3)
<i>Z</i>	1	4
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (mg m ⁻³)	1.398	1.423
<i>F</i> (000)	506	1992
Crystal size (mm)	0.11 × 0.18 × 0.29	0.13 × 0.17 × 0.23
<i>T</i> (K)	296	296
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.456	0.468
<i>R</i> ₁ ^a	0.0582	0.0457
<i>wR</i> ₂ ^b	0.1856	0.1155
GOF ^c	0.86	0.93
^a $R_1 = \frac{\sum F_o - F_c }{\sum F_o }$		
^b $wR_2 = \frac{[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2]]}{\sum [w(F_o^2)^2]}^{1/2}$		
^c GOF = $\frac{[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2]]}{(M - N)}^{1/2}$, where M is the number of reflections and N is the number of parameters refined.		

acterization (microanalysis, NMR and IR) data on both the complexes are found to correspond well with the expected composition, viz. [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂], indicating that purple-1 and purple-2 are probably two isomers of the same [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex. As the 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate anion is an unsymmetrical bidentate chelating ligand, five geometric isomers are possible for the [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex, which are shown in Fig. 1. These isomers are labeled in terms of the relative disposition of the pairs of nitrogen, oxygen and phosphorus atoms respectively¹². In order to authenticate composition of these two purple complexes, as well as to find out their stereochemistry, structure of each of them has been determined by X-ray crystallography. Structure of the purple-1 complex is shown in Fig. 2 and some relevant bond parameters are listed in Table 2. The structure shows that, as expected, two 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligands are indeed coordinated to ruthenium in the usual N,O-mode (**I**) and two PPh₃ ligands are also coordinated to the metal

Fig. 1. Possible geometric isomers of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complex.

Fig. 2. Structure of the ttt - $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complex. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

center. Examination of the relative disposition of the N, O and P donor atoms in this complex reveals that it has the ttt -geometry, where the two N,O-donor ligands are mutually *trans* and so are the two PPh_3 ligands. Therefore the purple-1 complex will henceforth be referred to

Table 2. Selected bond distances and bond angles for the ttt - and cct - $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complexes

ttt - $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$			
Bond distances (Å)			
Ru1-N1	2.024(5)	N1-O1	1.233(6)
Ru1-O2	2.078(3)	N1-C1	1.407(6)
Ru1-P1	2.3931(16)	C1-C2	1.400(8)
		C2-O2	1.263(7)
Bond angles (deg)			
N1-Ru1-O2	78.80(17)		
cct - $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$			
Bond distances (Å)			
Ru1-N1	1.976(2)	N1-O1	1.256(3)
Ru1-O2	2.096(2)	N1-C1	1.398(4)
Ru1-N2	1.993(2)	C1-C2	1.419(4)
Ru1-O4	2.089(2)	C2-O2	1.283(4)
Ru1-P1	2.3982(9)	N2-O3	1.263(3)
Ru1-P2	2.3985(9)	N2-C11	1.387(4)
		C11-C12	1.415(4)
		C12-O4	1.285(4)
Bond angles (deg)			
P1-Ru1-P2	177.43(3)	N1-Ru1-O2	79.11(9)
N1-Ru1-O4	177.38(9)	N2-Ru1-O4	78.78(9)
N2-Ru1-O2	178.25(9)		

as *ttt*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂]. The Ru-N, Ru-O and Ru-P distances are found to be normal², and the bond distances within the coordinated 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligand are found to be consistent with its resonance-hybrid structure (C)^{3b}. The N₂O₂P₂ coordination sphere around ruthenium is distorted significantly from ideal octahedral geometry, as reflected in the bond parameters around the metal center (Table 2). Crystal structure of the purple-2 complex (Fig. 3) shows that, as anticipated, two 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligands are again coordinated to ruthenium along with two PPh₃ ligands. However, in this complex

Fig. 3. Structure of the *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

the two coordinated 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligands are mutually *cis*. Hence, in view of relative disposition of the ligands this complex has the *cct* geometry. So the purple-2 complex will henceforth be referred to as *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂]. The observed metrical parameters in this *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex are found to compare well with those in the *ttt*-isomer (Table 2).

Formation of the *ttt* and *cct* isomers of the [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex from a simple reaction between [Ru(PPh₃)₃Cl₂] and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (**Hnn**) has been rather interesting. In order to find out the difference of thermodynamic stability between these two geometric isomers of [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂], DFT calculations have been performed on both the *ttt* and *cct* isomers⁸. The calculations show that the *ttt*-isomer is more stable than the *cct*-isomer by only 7.5 kcal/mol (Fig. 4). To examine the

feasibility of converting the *cct*-isomer into the thermodynamically more stable *ttt*-isomer, the *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex was taken up in a high-boiling solvent, viz. *ortho*-xylene (boiling point 144 °C), and refluxed for only 30 min. This thermal treatment has been found to transform *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] quantitatively to *ttt*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂], which has been identified by its characteristic electronic spectrum (*vide infra*).

Spectral studies :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements show that the *ttt*- and *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complexes are diamagnetic, which corresponds to the +2 state of ruthenium (low-spin *d*⁶, *S* = 0) in these complexes. ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes have been recorded in CDCl₃ solution, and the NMR spectral data are presented in the Experimental section. In both the complexes, signals from the two PPh₃ ligands have appeared as broad peaks within 6.94–7.49 ppm. The two coordinated 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligands are stereochemically equivalent in both the isomers, and hence six signals are expected signals from them. However, only three of these could be clearly identified in the *ttt*-isomer and two in the *cct*-isomer. Identification of the remaining signals has not been possible due to their overlap with the broad peaks from PPh₃.

Infrared spectra of the *ttt*- and *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complexes show many bands of different intensities in the 4000–450 cm⁻¹ region. No attempt has been made to assign each individual band to a specific vibration. However, three strong bands, displayed near 745, 695 and 520 cm⁻¹ by both the complexes, are attributable to the coordinated triphenylphosphines. Besides, comparison with the spectrum of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol shows that the O-H stretch, observed at 3066 cm⁻¹ in the uncoordinated ligand, is absent in the complexes, confirming dissociation of the phenolic proton upon complexation. A sharp and strong band displayed at 1096 cm⁻¹ by both the complexes is attributable to the ν_{C-O} stretch. The ν_{NO} vibration could be identified as a sharp band near 1290 cm⁻¹ in both the complexes.

The *ttt*- and *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complexes are found to be readily soluble in dichloromethane, chloroform, acetonitrile, etc., producing bright purple solutions. Electronic spectra of these complexes have been recorded in dichloromethane solution. Spectral data are presented in Table 3, and the spectra are shown in Fig. 5. Both the

Fig. 4. The energy difference between the *cct*- and *ttt*-isomers of the [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex.

Table 3. Electronic spectral and cyclic voltammetric data		
Complex	Electronic spectral data ^a λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Cyclic voltammetric data ^c E, V vs SCE
<i>ttt</i> -[Ru(PPh ₃) ₂ (nn) ₂]	519 (3410), 394 ^b (2040), 337 ^b (4120), 263 (15080), 231 (33130)	0.76 (84) ^d , -0.32 ^e
<i>cct</i> -[Ru(PPh ₃) ₂ (nn) ₂]	549 ^b (5620), 528 (5860), 380 ^b (2980), 334 ^b (4720), 262 (18090), 231 (29870)	0.86 ^f , -0.43 ^e

^aIn dichloromethane. ^bShoulder. ^cSolvent, acetonitrile; supporting electrolyte, TBHP; scan rate, 50 mV s⁻¹. ^d $E_{1/2}$ value [$E_{1/2} = 0.5 (E_{pa} + E_{pc})$, where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials respectively]. The ΔE_p ($\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$) value is given in parenthesis. ^e E_{pc} value. ^f E_{pa} value.

Fig. 5. Electronic spectra of *ttt*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] (—) and *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] (----) in dichloromethane solution.

complexes show several intense absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet regions. The absorptions in the ultraviolet region are attributable to transitions within the ligand orbitals. To have an insight into the nature of absorptions in the visible region, DFT calculations have been performed on both the isomers of the $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complex⁸. Compositions of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) are given in Table 4 and contour plots of these molecular orbitals are shown in Fig. 6. The HOMO

has major (>70%) contribution from the two 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligands, with much less (<30%) contribution from ruthenium, and almost negligible (<0.5%) contribution from the two PPh_3 ligands. The LUMO is delocalized mostly (>83%) on the 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligands, <16% on the metal center, and $\leq 0.6\%$ on the two PPh_3 ligands. Based on the compositions of the HOMO and LUMO, the lowest energy absorption displayed by these *ttt*- and *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complexes within 519–549 nm is assignable to an admixture of MLCT and LLCT transitions.

Table 4. Composition of selected molecular orbitals of the *ttt*- and *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complexes

Complex	Contributing fragments	% Contribution of fragments to	
		HOMO	LUMO
<i>ttt</i> - $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$	Ru	29.50	7.33
	PPh_3	0.44	0.59
	nn	70.06	92.08
<i>cct</i> - $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$	Ru	23.24	15.66
	PPh_3	0.30	0.60
	nn	76.46	83.74

Electrochemical properties :

Electrochemical properties of the *ttt*- and *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complexes have been studied by cyclic voltammetry in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP). Both the complexes show an oxidative response on the positive side of SCE and a reductive response on the negative side. The voltammograms are shown in Fig. 7 and voltammetric data are presented in Table 3. In view of composition of the HOMO in these complexes, the oxidative response is assigned to oxidation of coordinated 1-

Fig. 6. Contour plot of the HOMO and LUMO of the *ttt*- and *cct*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{nn})_2]$ complexes.

Fig. 7. Cyclic voltammograms of (a) *ttt*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] and (b) *cct*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complexes in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP) at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹.

nitroso-2-naphtholate ligand. Similarly, based on the composition of the LUMO, the reduction is also assigned to reduction of the coordinated 1-nitroso-2-naphtholate ligand. The oxidative response in the *ttt*-[Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex is quasi-reversible. All the other redox responses are found to be irreversible in nature.

Conclusion

The present study shows that 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (**Hnn**) readily reacts with [Ru(PPh₃)₃Cl₂] and affords two geometrical isomers, viz. *ttt* and *cct*, of the [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex. This study also demonstrates that conversion of the *cct*-isomer of the [Ru(PPh₃)₂(nn)₂] complex to the corresponding *ttt*-isomer, which is ther-

modynamically more stable, is possible by simple thermal agitation in refluxing *ortho*-xylene.

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Appendix A

Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC numbers 969170 and 969171.

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 - For example, *ttt* and *cct* respectively indicates *trans-trans-trans* and *cis-cis-trans* disposition of the N, O and P donor atoms.

